

ANALYSIS OF PRODUCT OF YIELD IN YARN SPINNING FROM RAW MATERIALS OF DIFFERENT DENSITIES

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Annotation. The article deals with the characteristics of raw materials, sketches and expired products in the justification of technological parameters of spinning from non-spun fiber in cotton-textile clusters. The paper describes the introduction of rational spinning options in production, direct transfer of fiber to the spinning process without spinning were compared on the basis of Uster Statistic 2018.

Keywords. Unpressed cotton fiber, fiber properties, sliver, roving, yarn, Uster HVI 1000 system, Uster Statistic 2018 indicators.

Cotton-textile clusters as a result of scientific research on the possibility of creating and implementing in production the harmonized technology of primary processing and spinning of cotton.

The technologies used in the cotton-textile clusters of Uzbekistan lag behind today's requirements. Cotton is processed seasonally and continues to be stored in open (bunts) area. In the world practice, storage of harvested cotton in mini bunts (model) has been introduced since 1970 [1].

In the United States, cotton picked by machine and packed in rolls is being transferred directly to processing without being stored in bunts. Reducing the costs of fiber pressing, transportation and storage of cotton fiber is now a priority in the production of expired products, 100% of cotton fiber is processed in the country [2].

There is also a traditional method of spinning, which causes a high degree of damage to the fibers in the production of cotton yarn. Repeated mechanical shocks in these technologies can severely damage the fibers, leading to a decrease in the quality of the spun yarn [3,4].

The presence of crude products in the sequence of spinning processes and the presence of tangled fibers and neps in the yarn was mainly determined by scientific research as a negative consequence of the technology of primary processing of cotton [5,6].

In order to study the quality of sketches and expired products in the production process, samples of sketches and yarns were prepared and practical experiments were carried out in the combined technology of unbleached cotton fibers (ginning fibers no bale opening directly mixed).

In the preparation of the sample, a sample of raw cotton from the "Sultan" selection was prepared at the ginnery "Boston Cluster" LLC, DP-130 gin, and unpainted fiber. Experimental work was carried out in two options under the conditions of production in the spinning mill of "Boston Mega Tekstil" LLC:

Experimental version, raw products and spun yarn were made from 4 types of non-pressed cotton fibers of the "Sultan" selection in a combined technology (ginning fibers no bale opening directly mixed);

Enterprise version, raw products and yarn were made from 4 types of cotton fiber of the "Sultan" selection in the current technology.

Experimental work was carried out in the spinning mill of "Boston Mega Tekstil" LLC on the basis of the plan of spinning yarn Ne 32/1 in the spin carding system, on the basis of standard norms established at the enterprise, and analyzed changes in the properties of sketches and yarn products.

According to the experimental option, the amount of returns, waste, sketches and yarn output at each technological transition was determined in an approved manner. Output of raw products prepared in the experimental option an increase of 1.13% compared to the enterprise option. Yarn yield was 86.89% in the control option and 88.03 % in the recommendation option, i.e. yarn yield increased by 1.14% (Table 1).

Table 1

Waste, sketch products and yarn output

№	Product and waste	In the enterprise option, %	In the experiment option, %
1.	Carding sliver output	89,17	90.30
2.	1 st transition of draw frame sliver output	88.72	89.85
3.	2 nd transition of draw frame sliver output	88.27	89.40
4.	Roving output	87.54	88.67
5.	Yarn output	86.89	88.03
	Total waste, %	13.11	11.97

Conclusion. This is a major advantage of the technology created side, because the fibers are not strongly compacted, in the cleaning-mixing and combing processes, a better quality sketch product is prepared than the traditional method, the output of the expired product is increased and appropriate cost-effectiveness in production is achieved.

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